

why the turner prize isn't enough to resolve a housing crisis

Matt Thompson considers what the award of the Turner Prize to a community housing project says about Britain's housing crisis – and how lessons from Liverpool's history of housing alternatives might inform urban policy

The news that Granby Four Streets Community Land Trust had won the 2015 Turner Prize was a sure sign of how deeply the housing crisis is being felt across Britain, not least in Liverpool.¹ The unprecedented award of the national art prize to a cutting-edge community-led housing project in Liverpool's Toxteth area not only reveals the extraordinary lengths to which the art world will go in causing controversy, breaking boundaries and subverting its own identity, but also signifies the vertiginous depth of the housing crisis.

Perhaps affordable housing should indeed be considered creative genius at a time when the vast majority of housing is not affordable to someone on the average UK wage. But the situation in Liverpool is not one of overheated housing markets and prices inflating beyond the reach of all but oligarchs and property speculators, but rather the polar opposite: characterised by 'housing market failure', where there simply is not enough demand to sustain buoyant prices, or enough residents to inhabit what quickly become empty homes.

But why has it been left to so-called art – rather than the City Council, a housing association or some publicly-funded regeneration programme – to resolve the neighbourhood decline and housing dereliction from which Granby, like many so many other inner-city neighbourhoods across the North, has suffered for decades? Part of the answer is that this is an issue, if not unique, then very specific to

Liverpool. For this particular project – in all its glorious contradictions – could not have emerged in any other city but Liverpool. Turner Prize-winning architects Assemble's innovative hands-on and do-it-yourself approach in Granby – where residents are not simply 'consulted' but take a leading role in the regeneration decision-making process – is the contemporary heir of an alternative strand in regeneration thinking with an especial affiliation with Liverpool's housing history.

A brief history of Liverpool housing

Liverpool has suffered a housing 'crisis' for at least the last two centuries. In the early 19th century, it revolved around material housing deprivation for the city's burgeoning working classes, mostly employed on the docks and housed in slum tenements in dense dockside neighbourhoods. In response, Liverpool City Council was one of the first local authorities in Europe to develop municipal housing,² and through several waves of public intervention in the inter-war and post-war periods much of the *material* housing deprivation was resolved.

However, as modernist municipal tenements replaced squalid 'back-to-back' speculatively built tenements, new forms of deprivation emerged. The 'Slum Clearance Programme' of the Labour Council from 1955 onwards began decanting residents of dense inner-city Liverpool out into the New Towns and 'overspill' outer estates being built on the

metropolitan periphery (in places like Kirkby and Skelmersdale), threatening to displace and break up tight-knit communities.

A growing number of Liverpool-based academics and commentators lay Liverpool's inner-city problem – of urban deprivation, housing vacancy and neighbourhood abandonment – at the door of public policy mistakes made in the post-war period.³ By the mid-1970s the Slum Clearance Programme had removed some 160,000 residents out of the urban core, helping to carve the ensuing long-term structural economic decline more firmly into the city's fabric. There was no doubt that the targeted terraces were in dire need of improvement or even replacing entirely – with no inside toilets, hot running water or electricity – but disagreement hinged on the best way to do this. Tenants resisted attempts by the City Council – disparagingly colloquialised as the 'Corpy' – to move them to seemingly random parts of the wider city-region, and began to organise themselves into pressure groups to challenge displacement.

The beginnings of an alternative

In the 1970s, these community groups found an unlikely ally in the embryonic housing association and community development movements then emerging across British inner cities. The 1969 Housing Act enabled councils to rehabilitate rather than demolish dilapidated terraced streets, and the Council invited Shelter, the newly formed homelessness campaigning charity, to experiment with new ideas in rehabilitation and community participation in the Shelter Neighbourhood Action Project – known by the snappy acronym SNAP – operating from 1969 to 1972 in the neighbourhood of Granby.⁴

SNAP's work with Granby residents set new precedents for participation in housing renewal; helped save the neighbourhood from demolition; and inspired development of the country's first rehabilitated housing co-ops in the early 1970s, which gave public tenants an unprecedented level of control over their living environments. The 1974 Housing Act laid the legislative foundations for a generous funding regime and support infrastructure for the development of housing associations and co-ops to provide an alternative to Corpy-delivered public housing. New charitable trusts and housing associations formed in Liverpool to capitalise on the incoming Liberal-led Council's favourable stance towards rehabilitation over demolition, delivered through housing associations and co-ops in General Improvement Areas.

One particular association, Cooperative Development Services (CDS), became the city's leading co-op development agency, and set about popularising the concept of co-ops among council tenants searching for an alternative solution to being

re-housed in Corpy properties scattered across the city. One such community, living in and around the Weller Streets, were particularly vocal and took the initiative to campaign for a co-op as a means of being kept together in good-quality housing. They worked closely with CDS to negotiate their way through what were complex planning, bureaucratic and financial procedures.⁵

Out of the creative collision between CDS and the Weller Street Co-op, a pioneering approach was born. The 'Weller Way' entailed the rejection of top-down technocratic management of municipal housing in favour of a radically participatory method which put residents in the driving seat of design, development and management for the first time in Liverpool's, and indeed Britain's, housing history.

The approach was elaborated theoretically by the late 'anarchist planner' Colin Ward, with his radical manifesto for 'collective dweller control'.⁶ There was great fervour at the time, expressed by professional participants and commentators alike, about the political potential for new-build co-operatives to revolutionise state-funded housing – to become 'Public Sector Housing 2.0' or 'Mark II'.⁷ Many residents were politicised by the opportunities presented by building their own co-op housing under collective dweller control and relative community autonomy. Getting involved in the highly political campaign process – often described as a 'battle' or 'fight' – radicalised and empowered many members to stand for election as Labour councillors, some of whom went on to support the further development of co-ops.⁸

From decentralisation to monopolisation

However, Liverpool's 'co-operative revolution' proved too short-lived for the ambitions for 'Public Sector Housing 2.0' to materialise. Events in local and national politics put paid to the further development of the movement. Locally, the Militant-led Labour Council of 1983-87 opposed and 'municipalised' co-ops on the basis that their apparent nepotistic exclusivity flew in the face of socialist principles of universal and egalitarian provision of municipal housing. Nationally, the Conservative Government's 1988 Housing Act threw out the baby (generous funding for co-ops under the 1974 Act) with the bathwater (stripping away the power of local authorities to provide housing and empowering the growing housing association sector, fuelled by private capital and increasingly commercialised practices, to step in and do a better job).

And in some sense this worked. The housing associations, in Liverpool at least, seemed to do a better job of providing effective management of social housing than the Corpy had done with municipal housing – for too long marred by sclerotic bureaucratic processes, long waiting lists, poor maintenance and repair backlogs, provoking tenant resistance in the form of rent strikes and the push for alternatives

From the late 1990s onwards, decline, housing vacancy and 'market failure' were becoming increasingly visible in neighbourhoods such as Granby

such as co-ops.⁹ With more professionalised and responsive management of the public housing stock, there followed a period of relative dormancy in housing activism through the 1990s and early 2000s.

But with their growth and commercialisation, the housing associations began to exhibit some of the very same problems that had been apparent before their promotion. At the peak of municipal housing, the Corpy managed some 90,000 homes in Liverpool – a figure which today covers the total stock held nationally by just one housing association once rooted in Liverpool (as Liverpool Improved Homes and then Merseyside Improved Houses) but now operating increasingly beyond the city-region as Riverside, one of the largest associations in the country, having all but shed its nominal ties to place.

Moreover, these big housing associations became implicated in the next round of state-led comprehensive urban renewal to hit inner-city Liverpool. The controversial Housing Market Renewal (HMR) Pathfinder programme involved the City Council working closely with preferred delivery partners, developers and housing associations to clear large areas of terraced houses, now deemed 'obsolete' for 21st century living.¹⁰ HMR emerged as a policy response to the 'wicked' problems of decline, housing vacancy and 'market failure' that were becoming increasingly visible in neighbourhoods like Granby from the late 1990s onwards. It was in Granby in particular that an especially problematic impasse was reached when sustained anti-demolition action by the Granby Residents' Association came up against Council-led proposals for the demolition of the last four streets left standing in the area that were first saved by SNAP activists and residents back in the early 1970s.¹¹

From the policy-maker's perspective, the problem was that the original rehabilitation work – completed first by SNAP and later by the housing associations in the 1970s; designed as a sticking plaster, not an antidote – was by the early 2000s nearing the end of its expected lifespan. In some cases the 19th-century terraced housing was literally falling in after years of insufficient maintenance by private landlords. While residents claimed that the Council, in consort with the housing associations, was intentionally driving the properties into the ground through a policy of 'managed decline' (which some saw as a punishment for the 1981 Toxteth riots), planners were looking for an affordable and deliverable solution to structural problems of economic decline manifesting themselves in the form of physical dereliction.

All agreed that *something* needed to be done to bring these houses back to life. The question remained what form such action should take.

Trapped in a ZOO

A deadlock in decision-making over possible regeneration solutions brought about by the remaining residents' vocal resistance to successive redevelopment proposals in Granby pushed the Council to adopt more extreme measures. Thus HMR was born as a more systematic, centrally funded and large-scale approach to address the perceived phenomenon of dereliction, abandonment and housing market failure – zoning off entire areas of low-demand housing to be parcelled up either for rehabilitation or for redevelopment by a public-private partnership of housing associations and developers. The idea was for one preferred developer to work with one preferred association in each 'Zone of Opportunity' so that stock could be

‘Creative resistance’ emerged in Granby, expressed through activities such as guerrilla gardening and monthly street markets

more effectively consolidated into land parcels for demolition and rebuild. Unfortunate homeowners within the Zones of Opportunity (given the equally unfortunate acronym ZOO) found themselves trapped in a spiral of negative equity.

In Granby, defiant homeowners’ property-based motivations and collective anger over ‘managed decline’ combined to produce a united local front against demolition.¹² Sitting down in front of approaching bulldozers and painting scaffolding on houses earmarked for clearance with anti-vandal paint – an ironic gesture imputing civic vandalism – certainly bought the protestors more time. But it was the more everyday, incremental, proactive and creative acts of transformation that eventually won them the day. Behind the scenes, a group of green-fingered residents had been engaging in ‘guerrilla gardening’ of the neglected streets and artistic rendering of the empty houses to transform the four streets into a green oasis, with monthly street markets bringing the community together and attracting visitors and vital sources of support¹³ (see below).

It was these acts of creative resistance that won the community the support they needed to push for a rehabilitation alternative to HMR – and eventually put the residents in touch with their architects, Assemble. After much internal debate, residents chose to form a Community Land Trust (CLT)¹⁴ to drive forward local desires for radical community control of the neighbourhood. This was the closest institutional model available that might allow residents to own and manage the housing themselves and provide affordable housing in perpetuity for local people, offering the scope to become a community body for the long-term regeneration and democratic control of the neighbourhood, protected from future demolition threats.

In many respects, the CLT model is a modern-day equivalent of the co-op model used in the area in the 1970s – but one recalibrated for the new legislative landscape, able to access grants and utilise funding where the co-op model no longer can. Unlike co-ops, CLTs separate the ownership of the buildings, which are leased out to individuals or groups, from that of the land on which they sit, owned collectively by the trust. And in fact, working with Granby Four Streets CLT is an eco co-op group called Terrace 21 (‘terraced housing for the 21st century’) – a key partner in the campaign and tenant of CLT land.

Coming full circle

The Granby CLT vision is the contemporary heir of SNAP and the co-op movement. The original founder of Terrace 21 happens to live in a nearby rehabilitated co-op house from the 1970s; and his father was one of the notable architects involved in pioneering the design democracy of the co-op movement. Many of the Granby CLT activists see their endeavour as finishing the work that SNAP started – rehabilitating four streets which map almost precisely onto the original SNAP boundaries, except for a few streets to the north which have been redeveloped in the interim.

Indeed, Assemble’s way of working bears many parallels with SNAP: utilising local skills and knowledge where possible for incremental do-it-yourself change; bringing residents directly into the planning process, encouraging mutual learning and empowerment with new skills and confidence; and incorporating aspects other than housing into the regeneration process, including education, training, jobs, environmental improvements and community activities, which together comprise a more holistic

alternative to HMR's more single-minded focus on improving the physical condition of the housing alone.

While HMR was conducted remotely, from the partnership offices headquartered in central Liverpool, Assemble architects have been living onsite in one of the empty homes and opened up shop in situ. Their new workshop on Granby Street, where many of the interior features of the rehabilitated houses are being crafted by local volunteers out of materials reclaimed from the houses, has provided new jobs for local people. This echoes the original SNAP Office, one of the first examples of an onsite office in regeneration programmes, with professionals embedding themselves within neighbourhoods for greater access and collaboration with residents.

There are clearly many difficulties and tensions that arise with such an immersive and intensive approach – not least the painstaking attention to detail and specificities of place, and the time-consuming dedication to hands-on onsite collaborative working with local residents. But there are countless benefits too. Distinctive quality of place is retained; history is incorporated rather than lost; residents are included in the process of reproducing place; new skills are learned; local jobs are created; confidence and pride in the community are given a boost; affordable homes are made available to those who need them, but protected from being sold off or consolidated into larger unmanageable stocks through the safeguards of community ownership built into the CLT model; and new cultures of co-operation and participatory local governance are instilled (and indeed institutionalised in the democratic practices governing the CLT).

Those undertaking future redevelopment schemes for 'hard-to-let' or low-demand housing could learn a great deal from these experiments and would do well to incorporate aspects of such approaches. Not only would they then be more likely to avoid the kind of controversy and opposition that dogged HMR, but there may also be additional positive spillover effects for more holistic and inclusive long-term social as well as physical renewal.

Granby CLT's recent success – with some ten houses having been transferred from the Council, and an overarching vision having been established for the wider regeneration of the neighbourhood by housing association partners – not only reveals what is possible when the collective will to transform urban space is backed up by the right resources, but also shows just how big a leap is yet to be taken if such projects are ever to be replicated on any significant scale. It took the whiff of a national art prize for politicians to wake up and smell the benefits of the Granby approach to regeneration, despite its historical precedents in SNAP and the co-op movement.

Contesting a powerful logic

Granby is not alone among CLT projects in Liverpool that have successfully contested the logic of property-led redevelopment deployed by HMR. The one other notable example is Homebaked in Anfield, which likewise has a close relationship with the art world, being a product of Liverpool Biennial, the city's high-profile festival of contemporary art.¹⁵ These projects demonstrate the positive power of art to resist destructive urban policies and enact transformative urban change. There is much for planners and policy-makers to learn here.

However, that it took the backing of the art world – either through funding or accolades – to give these projects the credibility they needed to gain the trust of policy-makers to become viable regeneration alternatives serves to highlight how removed such creative approaches have become from conventional urban policy; despite the fact that similar perspectives were once built into national and local state-funded programmes such as SNAP and the new-build co-operatives.

The gap between the professional and state support enjoyed by the 1970s co-op movement and that for today's CLT projects is huge. The co-ops were supported by a market of competing professional co-operative development agencies dedicated to the task of providing vital technical advice, education and skills training to new co-op groups for the sustained growth of the movement – crucially funded with generous grants covering full capital and some revenue costs, until the 1974 Housing Act was superseded by the 1988 Act.¹⁶ But today's CLT projects are woefully reliant on ad hoc sources of professional support, some small-scale government grants (such as those made through the Empty Homes Community Grants programme, which ran from 2012 to 2015), and otherwise private philanthropic funding and artistic benefactors.

While the National CLT Network does provide grant funding and technical advisors, which the Liverpool CLTs are using, this is driven from the national level, from offices in London, and lacks the kind of locally attuned and responsive regional presence and connection to place from which the co-op movement benefited.

There is no reason in principle why the approach pioneered by SNAP and developed through urban CLTs cannot be fully incorporated into the design of an HMR-like programme. Indeed, it was even explored and advocated as an option for HMR Pathfinders by sustainable urbanism consultancy URBED.¹⁷ But in practice perhaps such artistic interventions only ever emerge through resistance to state and market logics?

My recent doctoral research (on which this article draws) has revealed that the CLT idea seems to have travelled to Liverpool via policy networks connected to CLT advocates at URBED, eventually

finding traction in an ex-New Deal for Communities (NDC) Partnership in Kensington, Liverpool. Kensington NDC flirted with the CLT idea as a potential 'legacy vehicle' to take on its assets for further regeneration after the partnership was disbanded – including multiple sites zoned for HMR. Although this state-led experiment was ultimately unsuccessful owing to a lack of community buy-in (an essential pre-requisite for the development of truly community-led housing), it hints at how HMR could have been done differently, had the political will and resources been present from the beginning to embed the approach within communities, with the necessary education, training and resources.

In our post-crash era of 'austerity localism',¹⁸ the chances of seeing another round of well funded, centrally directed large-scale regeneration programmes like HMR are, at least in the short term, slim to none. Yet we surely cannot pin all our hopes of resolving the problems of inner-city decline and deprivation on a few artist-driven demonstration projects? There are simply not enough trendy London-based architectural collectives on course to rock the art world – nor public art projects curated by Liverpool Biennial – to go around, let alone to constitute a strategy for systemic intervention.

Kick-starting the Granby model – to make it 'go viral' across Liverpool and beyond¹⁹ – will obviously require more than just five minutes of fame from the Turner Prize. So how can urban policy and the small raft of existing resources available at the local and city-regional level be re-oriented towards supporting the more systematic development of projects like Granby Four Streets?

What is to be done?

What we need now is a new integrated system of physical and socio-economic regeneration driven by the next generation of state-funded Urban Development Corporations (UDCs) to co-ordinate the development of multiple localised community-led programmes. We can take our cue from the Merseyside Development Corporation first put in place by Michael Heseltine in the early 1980s. This was one of two pioneering UDCs across the country, set up partly in response to the 1981 Toxteth riots (a symptom of a wider socio-economic malaise gripping Liverpool), but which focused on property-led development and pump-priming of private sector investment.

This is where parallels with this 1980s neoliberal experiment should end. New UDCs would need to be much more accountable to local people. Democratic accountability and local responsiveness could be built into a federated structure of smaller-scale Community Development Corporations (CDCs) operating at an urban district scale – not unlike the more established CDC movement in the

US.²⁰ These CDCs would have powers to distribute funds and support services co-ordinated ultimately by the overarching UDC, in which they would have a stake in decision-making, with citizen representation on the governing boards. Although appearing radical in the current climate of austerity localism, such an approach is in fact not all that revolutionary. SNAP's final recommendations suggested something similar back in 1972: that a Task Force under the Cabinet Office should co-ordinate a decentralised Urban Programme of metropolitan development agencies.⁴

Crucial to the operation of such a system would be the consolidation of all currently under-used public land and assets and their transfer into UDC ownership, through the creation of some kind of City Region Land Bank. Empty housing, derelict land and disused public buildings could then be transferred over to community groups, legally incorporated as CLTs or Community Interest Companies (CICs), for instance, to be developed by and for local people. These would be overseen by CDCs and supported by professionals and experts procured by CDCs – in a similar vein to how, in the late 1970s, CDS worked closely with co-op groups to co-produce new-build housing developments.

It is important that all such assets are brought under community ownership through institutional vehicles such as CLTs. This will ensure that the assets remain under community and ultimately public control; prevent the private capture of value creation once economic recovery starts to take off; ensure that people are involved in the decision-making over how regeneration unfolds, with multiple spin-off benefits in terms of socio-economic and political empowerment; and allow for the full recycling of any financial surpluses back into the local area, so that regeneration eventually becomes a self-sustaining cycle once sufficient momentum builds. CLTs could become the nodes at the neighbourhood scale through which CDCs allocate funds and deliver professional support, doubling up as community 'anchors' through which all other forms of community development are organised.

Supporting the emergence and growth of community asset transfer initiatives such as CLTs in deprived communities suffering with empty stock and market failures is a first step. But it must involve the nurturing of community enterprises as spin-offs from the rehabilitation process and the more long-term provision of incubation spaces in some of the empty buildings brought back to life by CLT activity.

This is happening now in Granby: the rehabilitation process has produced a social enterprise specialising in the regeneration process itself, the Granby Workshop.²¹ Initiated by Assemble, and starting out with four paid employees and mostly volunteers, Granby Workshop has created many new jobs for local people, now with some 14 paid positions. The

The rehabilitation process in Granby has produced the Granby Workshop – a social enterprise specialising in the regeneration process itself

ultimate aim is to provide new space for community businesses in some of the CLT-owned buildings after the physical rehabilitation process has been completed, acting as the beginnings of a newly revitalised high street and a more permanent location for the popular street market which helped to inspire the whole process.

Although such a structure seems unlikely to be adopted in the present political climate, the institutional architecture is already partly in place in Liverpool, left over from the co-operative movement, or indeed slowly beginning to fall into place through the move towards city-regional governance under devolution. First, the modern incarnation of CDS is still going strong – as North West Housing Services, a non-profit social enterprise which manages the professional services for the some 50 co-ops quietly enduring across Merseyside to this day. North West Housing Services is no longer the radical co-op development agency it once was, but it nonetheless has the right resources, connections and institutional memory to potentially reinvigorate the co-operative movement from its long dormancy and promote new growth.

There is a growing realisation that the Merseyside co-ops are sitting on a large surplus.²² If North West Housing Services can bring the co-ops together to act collectively, as they once did as CDS with the now-disbanded Merseyside Federation of Housing Co-ops, then these surpluses – if successfully amalgamated into a central pot – could be used to fund the next generation of housing co-ops, or indeed CLTs. North West Housing Services has recently supported Granby CLT with pro bono professional advice and low-interest loans, but more

needs to be done to harness the untapped resources and knowledge of the latent co-op support infrastructure in Merseyside. The best way to support their growth beyond a few demonstration projects is through the establishment of an equivalent agency such as CDS/North West Housing Services for CLTs.

There are a whole host of organisations capable of offering support and getting involved in the creation of CLTs and CDCs – from North West Housing Services to the National CLT Network. But for this system to really take off, we need local and city-regional government to think more creatively about how to make the most of newly devolved powers. Devolution presents many opportunities to do things differently.

From May 2017, the Liverpool City Region Combined Authority and the new elected City Region Mayor – working alongside the Local Enterprise Partnership – will receive greater powers over planning, transport, skills, enterprise and housing as part of the devolution deal.²³ If we are serious about tackling the ‘wicked’ problems of housing market failure, neighbourhood decline and spatially concentrated poverty, we need to radically rethink how we approach local economic development – to link it up more creatively with housing, enterprise, health and education. These seemingly detached areas of policy need to be reconfigured to work directly for deprived communities; incorporated as central elements in an integrated urban policy. What we need now is a real political commitment to back the systematic incubation of new forms of creative social innovation of the kind that has transformed Granby.

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Notes

- 1 See, for example, D. Foster: 'Assemble's Turner prize win: a sign of our deeply embedded housing crisis'. *The Guardian*, 8 Dec. 2015. www.theguardian.com/housing-network/2015/dec/08/assemble-turner-prize-housing-crisis-toxteth; and C. Higgins: 'Turner prize winners Assemble: 'Art? We're more interested in plumbing''. *The Guardian*, 8 Dec. 2015. www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2015/dec/08/assemble-turner-prize-architects-are-we-artists
- 2 See the Municipal Dreams blog, at <https://municipaldreams.wordpress.com/2013/10/08/liverpool-first-council-houses-in-europe/>
- 3 See, for instance: O. Sykes, J. Brown, M. Cocks, D. Shaw and C. Couch: 'A City Profile of Liverpool'. *Cities*, 2013, Vol. 35, Dec., 299-318; T. Lane: *Liverpool: City of the Sea*. Liverpool University Press, 1997, Second Edition; and *Merseyside in Crisis*. Merseyside Socialist Research Group. Manchester Free Press, 1980
- 4 D. McConaghy: *Another Chance for Cities: SNAP 69-72*. SNAP Final Report. Shelter Neighbourhood Action Project, 1972
- 5 A. McDonald: *The Weller Way: The Story of the Weller Street Housing Cooperative*. Faber & Faber, 1986
- 6 C. Ward: *Tenants Take Over* (Architectural Press, 1974). This book, in particular, was influential in the development of the Weller Streets, as evident in this personal interview: 'The book had a salutary effect in Liverpool during a brief period when the Liberals controlled the city's housing policy. It inspired several instances... of newly-built housing where the tenants of old slum houses were enabled to find a site, and commission an architect to design their own new housing... The proudest moment of my housing advocacy was when the Weller Street Coop chairman, Billy Floyd, introduced me at a meeting by waving a tattered copy of *Tenants Take Over* and saying: 'Here's the man who wrote the Old Testament... But we built the New Jerusalem!' C. Ward and D. Goodway: *Talking Anarchy*. Five Leaves Publications, 2003, pp.74-5
- 7 'What's happening now, in Liverpool, is that a new form of public sector housing is being developed; and it's not just co-ops, it's new-build co-ops. Only through new-building do you have the opportunity to shape an environment. And it's going to be... a major, possibly dominant, form of public housing in the twentieth century. And the Weller Streets would have been the model.' Interview with Paul Lusk, quoted in *The Weller Way* (see note 5, p. 208). 'There's a possibility here of genuinely public housing mark 2. Instead of the state or the Corpy being in charge and doing a miserable job, why can't people who don't have educational qualifications, don't have often much of an employment, don't have the money; why can't they nonetheless be in charge of running their own estates?' Interview with Liverpool Liberal councillor as part of the author's PhD, in 2013
- 8 Phil Hughes, for instance, was inspired to become a Labour councillor through his role as treasurer of the Weller Street Co-op, and used his new position of power, as Chair of Housing when Labour were re-elected in 1987, to help push through plans for the Langrove Co-op in Everton, which had up until that point been struggling against Militant opposition to co-ops – See 'The Langrove Action Story' webpage, at <http://togetherforthecommongood.co.uk/case-studies/articles/the-langrove-action-story.html>
- 9 T. Mars: 'Housing in Liverpool 8'. *ROOF*, 1981, Vol. 6 (5); and A. Grosskurth: 'Bringing back the Braddocks'. *ROOF*, 1985, Vol. 10 (1), 19-23
- 10 D. Webb: 'Rethinking the role of markets in urban renewal: the Housing Market Renewal initiative in England'. *Housing, Theory & Society*, 2010, Vol. 27 (4), 313-31; and I. Cole: 'Housing Market Renewal and demolition in England in the 2000s: the governance of 'wicked problems''. *International Journal of Housing Policy*, 2012, Vol. 12 (3), 347-66
- 11 A. Merrifield: 'Them and us: rebuilding the ruins in Liverpool'. In *Dialectical Urbanism*. Monthly Review Press, 2002, pp.53-73
- 12 T. Duffy: 'Peaceful protest on Toxteth street forces demolition men to down tools'. *Liverpool Echo*, 12 Jul. 2011. www.liverpoolecho.co.uk/news/liverpool-news/peaceful-protest-toxteth-street-forces-3369896
- 13 See the A Sense of Place blog, at <https://asenseofplaceblog.wordpress.com/2015/06/10/granby-4-streets-telling-the-story/>
- 14 M. Thompson: 'Between boundaries: from commoning and guerrilla gardening to Community Land Trust development in Liverpool'. *Antipode* 2015, Vol. 47 (4), 1021-42. Available at <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/anti.12154/abstract>
- 15 J. Van Heeswijk and B. Jurgensen: 'Introduction'. *Stages #2: Homebaked: A Perfect Recipe*. Liverpool Biennial journal, 2014. www.biennial.com/journal/
- 16 *Building Democracy: Housing Cooperatives on Merseyside*. Update '94. Cooperative Development Services (Liverpool) Ltd., 1994; D. Clapham and K. Kintrea: *Housing Co-Operatives in Britain*. Longman, 1992; G. Towers: *Building Democracy: Community Architecture in the Inner Cities*. Routledge, 1995
- 17 *Werneth/Freehold Renewal*. Report for Oldham Local Strategic Partnership and North West Development Agency. URBED, 2004. <http://urbed.coop/sites/default/files/Oldham%20Beyond%20Werneth.pdf>
- 18 D. Featherstone, A. Ince, D. Mackinnon, K. Strauss and A. Cumbers: 'Progressive localism and the construction of political alternatives'. *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, 2012, Vol. 37 (2), 177-82
- 19 T. Moore and D. Mullins: 'Scaling-Up or Going-Viral: Comparing Self-Help Housing and Community Land Trust Facilitation'. Working Paper 94, Third Sector Research Centre, Mar. 2013. www.birmingham.ac.uk/generic/tsrc/documents/tsrc/working-papers/working-paper-94.pdf
- 20 D.L. Imbroscio: *Reconstructing City Politics: Alternative Economic Development and Urban Regimes*. SAGE Publications, 1997
- 21 See the Granby Workshop website, at www.granbyworkshop.co.uk/
- 22 Having long ago paid off mortgages whose repayments were calculated on the basis of far lower 'fair' rents before the higher 'affordable' rents kicked in after the 1988 Housing Act, the Merseyside co-ops are making large annual surpluses which are far greater than is required for maintenance
- 23 See the Liverpool City Region Devolution Agreement at www.gov.uk/government/publications/liverpool-devolution-deal